

Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cobalt(III) with Dimethylglyoxime

RAJIB LAL DE* and SANJIB KUMAR BHAR

Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

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Mixed-ligand complexes of cobalt(III) of the types $[\text{Co}(\text{SBx})(\text{DMGH})]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{SBy})(\text{DMGH})]$, where SBx = dianion of tetradentate Schiff base; SBy = monoanion of bidentate Schiff base; DMGH = monoanion of dimethylglyoxime, were isolated from the reaction of alcoholic suspension of cobalt(III) dimethylglyoximate dihydrate with Schiff bases in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios for SBx and SBy respectively. Further mixed-ligand complexes of the types $[\text{Co}(\text{SBy})_2(\text{Lig})]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{SBy})(\text{Lig})_2]$, where Lig = monoanion of acetylacetonate or monoanion of salicylaldehyde, were also obtained when preoxidised solution of cobalt(III) acetylacetonate dihydrate and cobalt(III) salicylaldehyde dihydrate were treated with bidentate Schiff bases in 1 : 2 molar ratios. Non-planar arrangement of the Schiff bases and the bidentate ligand anions occupying *cis*-positions around cobalt(III) ion have been suggested.

Cobalt(III) mixed-ligand complexes involving tetradentate Schiff bases and bidentate ligands have been the subject of study¹ especially because of the fact that in presence of bidentate ligands, the usually planar tetradentate Schiff bases attain a non-planar conformation leaving the two *cis*-positions to get occupied by the bidentate ligands as revealed by the single crystal X-ray crystallographic investigation².

Dimethylglyoxime is an unique bidentate ligand and its bonding with transition metals usually takes a different course than in case of other common bidentate ligands like acetylacetonate, salicylaldehyde etc. With a view to investigate the feasibility of the formation of mixed-ligand complexes of cobalt(III) involving Schiff bases and dimethylglyoxime, some reactions have been performed and the results are being reported here.

Results and Discussion

Reactions leading to the formation of the mixed-ligand cobalt(III) complexes and particularly those with $\text{Co}(\text{DMGH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were found to be slow. But in a little ammoniacal medium, the reactions proceeded at a much faster rate and the yields also increased appreciably.

All the compounds (Table 1) insoluble in water and those involving DMGH were less soluble in ethanol, methanol, chloroform and in other common organic solvents compared to those involving acac and sal. All the compounds were diamagnetic or only feebly paramagnetic.

The electronic spectral data are tabulated in Table 2. All the complexes show bands at around 48 000–40 000, 29 000–26 000, 21 000–20 000 and 19 000–16 000 cm^{-1} which are very close to the pseudo-octahedral cobalt(III) bands³. The assignments of the bands around 21 000–20 000 and 19 000–16 000 cm^{-1} may be made as the split components of the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transition, whereas the bands around 29 000–26 000 cm^{-1} are due to the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transition mixed up with the metal (t_{2g}) \rightarrow ligand (π^*) transition. The acac anion however absorbs⁴ around 26 000 cm^{-1} and the intra-ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the DMGH anion, so also the imidazole \rightarrow cobalt transitions⁵ appear near 29 000 cm^{-1} . The bands around 40 000 cm^{-1} may also be assigned as due to ligand (σ_L) \rightarrow metal (e_g) and the high energy bands near 46 000 cm^{-1} may be due to the metal ($d\pi$) \rightarrow oxime (π^*) transitions⁶.

The appearance of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ bands at 1640–1610

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Complex/ (colour)	M.p. ^o C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. wt. : Found/(Calcd.)
			C	H	N	Co	
1	Co(SALEN)(DMGH) (Reddish brown)	282d	53.92 (54.55)	4.66 (4.81)	12.93 (12.72)	14.05 (13.38)	440 ^a (440.3)
2	Co(SALPN)(DHGH) (Reddish brown)	312d	54.83 (55.51)	4.88 (5.10)	12.05 (12.33)	13.26 (12.97)	—
3	Co(SALOP) ₂ (DMGH) (Blackish brown)	261d	61.04 (60.21)	4.72 (4.55)	9.67 (9.36)	10.16 (9.84)	—
4	Co(SALENOL) ₂ (DMGH) (Deep brown)	205d	53.21 (52.54)	5.65 (5.42)	11.54 (11.15)	11.62 (11.73)	502 ^a (502.4)
5	Co(SAN) ₂ (DMGH) (Blackish brown)	245d	64.00 (63.63)	5.01 (4.77)	10.06 (9.89)	10.14 (10.41)	—
6	Co(SALOP) ₂ (acac) (Greenish brown)	222d	63.28 (63.92)	4.77 (4.67)	5.01 (4.80)	10.50 (10.12)	582 ^a (582.5)
7	Co(SALENOL) ₂ (acac) (Brownish red)	202d	57.11 (56.79)	5.89 (5.59)	5.64 (5.76)	11.94 (12.12)	—
8	Co(SAN) ₂ (acac) (Black)	219d	68.22 (67.64)	4.88 (4.94)	5.27 (5.09)	11.11 (10.71)	—
9	Co(SALOP) ₂ (sal) (Deep brown)	201d	65.14 (65.57)	4.35 (4.17)	4.87 (4.63)	10.18 (9.75)	—
10	Co(SALENOL) ₂ (sal) (Orange red)	192d	58.54 (59.06)	5.12 (4.96)	5.32 (5.51)	11.93 (11.59)	508 ^a (508.4)
11	Co(SALOP)(acac) ₂ (Brown)	236d	59.20 (58.85)	5.40 (5.15)	2.74 (2.98)	13.08 (12.55)	—
12	Co(SALENOL)(acac) ₂ (Pale brown)	214d	54.82 (54.16)	5.87 (5.74)	3.18 (3.32)	13.09 (13.98)	421 ^a (421.3)
13	Co(SALOP)(sal) ₂ (Brown)	198d	62.68 (63.17)	4.13 (3.93)	2.90 (2.73)	11.26 (11.48)	—
14	Co(SALENOL)(sal) ₂ (Deep red)	191d	60.10 (59.36)	4.60 (4.33)	3.17 (3.01)	12.82 (12.66)	—
15	Co(SALOP) ₃ (Brownish green)	259	67.11 (67.34)	4.49 (4.35)	6.23 (6.04)	8.25 (8.47)	—
16	Co(SALENOL) ₃ (Brownish red)	250	58.42 (58.80)	5.82 (5.48)	7.78 (7.62)	11.02 (10.68)	—

^aEI-MS

cm⁻¹ (Table 2) indicated the presence of coordinated C=N groups of the Schiff bases⁷. The bands at around 1560 cm⁻¹ is attributable to $\nu_{C=N}$ of the dimethylglyoximate ligand⁸. The band is not affected much by the change of the Schiff base ligand. The bands around 1590 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to $\nu_{C...O}$ of the acetylacetonate anion⁹. Despite some controversy, arising from the appearance of $\nu_{C=N}$ and $\nu_{C=C}$ modes of the Schiff bases, the spectral data indicate clearly the presence of N-bonded dimethylglyoxime and O-bonded acetylacetonate. The bands around 1240 and 1090 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{N-O}

vibration¹⁰. The bands at 510 cm⁻¹ is attributed to ν_{Co-N} vibrations between Co and N atoms of the dimethylglyoxime ligands⁸, whereas the bands around 540 and 470 cm⁻¹ are assignable to ν_{Co-N} vibrations between Co and N of the Schiff base ligands and ν_{Co-O} respectively¹¹.

Experimental

C, H and N analysis were obtained from C.D.R.I., Lucknow, and cobalt was estimated by spectrophotometric method. Mass spectra were obtained from C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Infrared spectra

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC AND IR (cm⁻¹) SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd no	Complex	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)(log ϵ)	$\nu_{C=N(SB)}$	$\nu_{C=N(DMGH)}/\nu_{C=O}$	ν_{N-O}	ν_{N-O}	$\nu_{Co-N(SB)}$	$\nu_{Co-N(DMGH)}$	ν_{Co-N}
1	Co(SALEN)(DMGH)	^a 46 686, 41 911sh, 40 085, 26 035, 18 094, 17 215	1 645–1 646 (doublet)	1 561	1 236	1 093	534	516	465
2	Co(SALPN)(DMGH)	^a 46 880, 41 804br, 40 000, 29 222, 26 335, 21 274, 20 052sh, 17 880, 16 725sh	1 636	1 560	1 232	1 092	539	515	468
3	Co(SALOP) ₂ (DMGH)	^a 46 985sh, 37 210, 27 544, 20 666, 17 335	1 625	1 565	1 231	1 089	542	517	470
4	Co(SALENOL) ₂ (DMGH)	^a 46 900, 35 820sh, 28 212, 26 333, 21 112sh, 16 824	1 612	1 562	1 227	1 089	538	515	466
5	Co(SAN) ₂ (DMGH)	^a 47 015sh, 37 600, 28 010, 20 985br, 19 682	1 598	1 566	1 230	1 091	540	518	471
6	Co(SALOP) ₂ (acac)	38 220sh, 26 705 (3.91), 20 526sh, 16 818 (2.55)	1 630–1 620 (doublet)	1 588			536		468
10	Co(SALENOL) ₂ (sal)	39 095sh, 26 408 (3.79), 20 308 (3.05), 17 125 (2.48)	1 615				544		470
11	Co(SALOP)(acac) ₂	39 000 (4.49), 26 108 (3.88), 20 008 (2.93), 16 422sh	1 621	1 584–1 588br			541		471
14	Co(SALENOL)(sal) ₂	38 555 (4.80), 26 315 (3.69), 21 000 (2.78), 16 118 (2.42)	1 611				536		469
15	Co(SALOP) ₃	40 305 (4.64), 36 565sh, 26 666 (3.70), 22 405 (3.02)	1 632				543		474

^aInsufficiently soluble in EtOH.

(KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 297 and 577 spectrophotometers and electronic spectra (EtOH) on a Hitachi U3400 spectrophotometer.

The amines, salicylaldehyde, acetylacetone and dimethylglyoxime were used as purchased. Cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate was purified by recrystallisation from acetic acid before use.

The Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation of salicylaldehyde with ethylenediamine (SALENH₂), 1,3-diaminopropane (SALPNH₂), *o*-aminophenol (SALOPH), ethanolamine (SALENOLH) and aniline (SANH) in appropriate molar ratios in refluxing ethanol. All the Schiff bases except SALENOLH were found to be crystalline solids and purified through crystallisation from ethanol. SALENOLH could not be isolated in the solid state and its reactions were performed in situ.

The dihydrates of cobalt(II) dimethylglyoximate¹², cobalt(II) acetylacetonate¹³ and cobalt(II) salicylaldehyde¹⁴ were prepared by the literature methods.

The mixed-ligand complexes : An ethanolic suspension of Co(DMGH)₂·2H₂O (DMGH = monoanion of dimethylglyoxime) was added to ethanolic solutions of the Schiff bases in either 1 : 1 (for SB_x) or 1 : 2 (for SB_y) molar ratios and warmed on a water-bath in presence of a few drops of ammonia for 1 h under frequent stirring followed by vigorous refluxing for 2 h. It was then filtered hot and the clear filtrate on reduction of volume, was subjected to column chromatography on a silica gel column (1.5 × 50 cm) for the separation of products, and eluted with ethanol. In each case, a yellow to orange-yellow fraction came out first which were identified as the unreacted Schiff bases. The dark coloured fraction, obtained as the middle fraction, on evaporation of the solvent and recrystallisation from ethanol yielded brown to dark-brown coloured complexes 1, 2 and 3–5 (Table 1) with tetradentate and bidentate Schiff bases respectively.

Pre-oxidised ethanolic suspension of Co(Lig)₂·2H₂O (Lig = acac, monoanion of acetylacetone

and sal, monoanion of salicylaldehyde) in presence of few drops of ammonia was added to ethanolic solutions of the Schiff bases, SBy in 1 : 2 molar ratios and refluxed vigorously for 3 h. It was then filtered hot and the clear filtrate on reduction of volume was subjected to column chromatography on a silica gel column (1.5 × 50 cm) for the separation of the products and eluted with ethanol. Four different fractions were obtained in each case and the first yellow fractions were identified as the unreacted Schiff bases. Three dark coloured fractions were then successively isolated and evaporated, and brown to dark coloured products were obtained by recrystallisation from ethanol. Complexes **6–10** were obtained from the second fractions, the third fractions yielded complexes **11–14** and complexes **15** and **16** (Table 1) were obtained from the fourth fractions.

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